

Dorothee Rusque

Post-doctoral researcher, Marie Curie Sklodowska – EUTOPIA-SIF Co-fund (Horizons 2020)
CY Cergy Paris University, CY Advanced Studies, Heritage, 1 rue Descartes, 95 000 Neuville-sur-Oise
Doctor in Modern History, University of Strasbourg, EA 3400 ARCHE

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CY Advanced studies: <https://eutopia-university.eu/english-version/sif-post-doctoral-fellowships/sif-2nd-cohort-fellows-dorothee-rusque-cy-cergy-paris-universite>

CY Cergy Paris University, Heritage: <https://heritages.cyu.fr/version-francaise/chercheur-es-temporaires/dorothee-rusque>

Research areas:

History of the Eighteenth-Century Europe, History of Science, History of Knowledge, Global History, Material History, Natural History, Collections, Heritage and museums, Travels, Circulations

EDUCATION

PhD – History 2012-2018

University of Strasbourg, Faculty of Historical Sciences, EA 3400 ARCHE, ED 519

Dissertation title: “*The Dialogue of Objects. Production and Circulation of Naturalist Knowledge: the case of Jean Hermann’s Collections (1738-1800)*”

Date: 29/06/2018

Supervisor: Isabelle Laboulais, professor in Modern History, University of Strasbourg

Master 2 – Social Studies of Science and Technology 2007

University of Strasbourg

Admission to CAPES in History and Geography (French Ministry of Education’s Concours) 2003

Master 2 – History 2002

University of Strasbourg, Faculty of Historical Sciences

PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE

Post-doctoral fellow, Marie Curie Sklodowska – EUTOPIA-SIF Co-fund 2022-2024

CY Cergy Paris University, CY Advanced Studies (France)

Heritage (UMR 9022)

Project: “*A World of Natural Specimens. Jacob Forster’s Family Business and the rise of the Globalized Market of Natural History in the Eighteenth-Century Europe*”

At the crossroads of global history, material history, economy and science, the project explores the modalities of the naturalist market’s globalization in the 18th and 19th Europe. It attempts to capture the naturalist trade by examining the role of dealers - especially the case of the Forsters’ family business -, the commoditization of Nature and the interconnexions between scientific and commercial knowledge. The

analysis combines different scales of observation, by paying attention to the main sites of the European naturalist market and its global expansion through the exchange networks and circulation of natural specimens within the British and Spanish empires.

Project: <https://eutopia-university.eu/english-version/sif-post-doctoral-fellowships/sif-2nd-cohort-fellows-dorothee-rusque-cy-cergy-paris-universite>

Post-doctoral fellow, Swiss National Science Foundation 2020-2022
University of Neuchâtel, Department of Literature and Knowledge

Project Sinergia: “*Botanical legacies from the Enlightenment: unexplored collections and texts at the crossroads between the humanities and the sciences*”

At the crossroads between the humanities and the sciences, the research project focuses on the botanical collections of Jean-Jacques Rousseau (1712-1778) and of several botanists who contributed to his herbarium. It questions botanical practices and knowledge in the 18th century, by examining the historical and scientific value of ancient herbaria, and the possibilities of providing these complex collections online.

Project: <https://botanical-legacies.unine.ch>

Jean-Jacques Rousseau virtual herbarium: <https://lesherbiersderousseau.org>

Recruitment campaign 2020-2023

Auditioned by the University of Caen (3rd) and Besançon (4th)

Assistant Lecturer – Modern History Sept. 2018 – Aug. 2019
University of Strasbourg, Faculty of Historical Sciences

Assistant Lecturer – Modern History Sept. 2015 – Aug. 2017
University of Strasbourg, Faculty of Historical Sciences

Doctoral researcher with teaching mission 2012-2015
University of Strasbourg, Faculty of Historical Sciences

Secondary School Teacher (History and Geography) 2004-2012/2017-2018

RESEARCH

▪ PUBLICATIONS

Articles in peer reviewed journals

With Thibaud Martinetti, “Fusée-Aublet's methodology in French Guiana (1762-1764): from collecting to the systematic inventory of the *Histoire des plantes de la Guiane française* (1775)”, *Archives of Natural History* [accepted, to be published].

Abstract: As part of the Kourou Expedition (1762-1764), the botanist Jean-Baptiste Christophe Fusée-Aublet was sent to French Guiana to prospect the colony's natural resources and draw up reports with a view to exploiting them. This mission enabled Fusée-Aublet to collect plants in the Amazon rainforest and on colonial dwellings with the help of crews made up of Indians, slaves and colonists. Thanks to the plants collected in his herbaria, his botanical registers in which he described these plants, and the shipping of specimens to Paris, Fusée-Aublet was able, on his return to France, to write his *Histoire des plantes de la Guiane Française* (1775). Based on the botanist's numerous archives in Paris and London, this paper looks at the two stages of this botanical adventure, the herborisation in the field and the work of determining the plants in Paris, with the aim of reconstructing the material conditions of this undertaking and restoring the botanical methodology that led to the publication of the *Histoire des plantes de la Guiane française*.

« Les voyageurs comme ressources de l'économie sociale du savoir au XVIII^e siècle. Les enseignements du registre des visiteurs du cabinet de Jean Hermann », *Viativa*, 10, 2023 [online].

URL: <https://dx.doi.org/10.52497/viatica2484>

Abstract: The sedentary nature of the Strasbourg naturalist Jean Hermann (1738-1800) made him a cabinet scientist. Although he travelled little, the university professor attracted more than 5,000 people to his natural history cabinet. The visitors' register (1762-1800), which is associated with a register of auditors of private lessons in natural history, shows the cabinet as a centre of attraction for the naturalist province in the 18th century. This document is a first-hand source for observing European mobility, particularly the practices associated with the Grand Tour and scholarly travel. It shows that the provincial cabinets were at the heart of the link between travel and natural history, as they were places of scholarly and curious sociability for the European visitors. In addition to representing an important part of Jean Hermann's social capital, travellers also provided him the resources necessary for the practice of natural history from a distance.

« Les réseaux d'échanges des spécimens naturels en Europe au XVIII^e siècle: le cas des collections de Jean Hermann », *Encyclopédie d'histoire numérique de l'Europe*, Paris Sorbonne University, 2022 [online].

URL: <https://ehne.fr/fr/node/21835>

« Observer à partir des collections d'histoire naturelle au XVIII^e siècle. Le dialogue des objets au sein du cabinet de Jean Hermann », *Epistemocritique*, 2017, p. 81-93.

URL: http://rnx9686.webmo.fr/wp-content/uploads/2017/07/08_Rusque_Hermann_06_17.pdf

« Faire circuler les objets naturalistes au XVIII^e siècle. Jean Hermann comme intermédiaire dans les échanges entre la France méridionale et l'espace germanique », *Liame*, 26, 2016 [online].

URL: <https://doi.org/10.4000/liame.568>

« Un dispositif matériel et visuel constitutif de la construction du savoir naturaliste au XVIII^e siècle: la collection de livres de Jean Hermann », *Histoire et civilisation du livre. Revue internationale*, Genève, Librairie Droz, tome XI, 2015, p. 95-108.

URL: <https://revues.droz.org/index.php/HCL/article/view/2317/3871>

« Construire et organiser le savoir naturaliste au XVIII^e siècle: la collection de livres de Jean Hermann », *La Revue de la BNU*, n° 10, 2014, p. 33-43.

URL: <https://savoirs.app/fr>

Books chapters

« Échanges et circulation des objets naturalistes dans la correspondance de Jean Hermann au XVIII^e siècle », in Marie BARRAL-BARON DAUSSY and Hugues DAUSSY (dir.), *Des objets en toutes lettres. La circulation des objets en Europe par les canaux épistolaires (XVI^e-XX^e siècles)*, Turnhout, Brepols, [accepted, to be published].

Abstract: The correspondence of the professor Jean Hermann (1738-1800), owner of a rich natural history cabinet, offers the opportunity to observe in detail the generalization of exchanges of natural specimens within the naturalist Republic of the 18th century. It highlights the plasticity of the forms of sociability associated with exchanges that combined the disinterested gift, the gift/counter-gift system and institutional collaboration linked to his function as director of the botanical garden of the university of Strasbourg. The circulation of objects required material procedures and numerous intermediaries to package and transfer them across Europe. Above all, the exchange networks appear as an essential resource in the construction of scientific knowledge. The scholarly reputation of naturalists was assessed according to the scientific value of the samples received, which could also be reappropriated by the correspondents responsible for redistributing them as intermediaries. While the geographical position of the correspondents proved decisive in extending the boundaries of the collection, they mainly exchanged objects taken from the surroundings. The exchange economy thus demonstrates the importance of local knowledge in the inventory of the natural world in the 18th century.

« Les réseaux russes de Jean Hermann, professeur d'histoire naturelle à l'université de Strasbourg », in Alexandra VESELOVA and Rodolphe BAUDIN (dir.), *Louis Henri de Nicolay, un intellectuel strasbourgeois dans la Russie des Lumières*, Strasbourg, Presses universitaires de Strasbourg, 2020, p. 53-70.

« Associer les textes aux collections. Les systèmes d'écriture du naturaliste Jean Hermann au XVIII^e siècle », in Emmanuelle CHAPRON and François PUGNIERE (dir.), *Écriture épistolaire et construction des savoirs au 18^e siècle. Jean-François Séguier et ses correspondants*, Paris, Éditions Classiques Garnier, 2019, p. 47-63.

« Construire le savoir minéralogique à partir d'une collection de minéraux au XVIII^e siècle. Le cabinet d'histoire naturelle de Jean Hermann », in Marc CLUET, Anne FELER and Gerhard HEIDE (éd.), *Die Würde des Minerals. Ein deutsches und zugleich universelles Anliegen*, Würzburg, Königshausen & Neumann, 2019, p. 333-346.

« Enseigner à partir des collections d'histoire naturelle au XVIII^e siècle. Les pratiques pédagogiques du professeur Jean Hermann », in Peter MARTI and Robert SEIDEL (dir.), *Die Universität Straßburg zwischen Späthumanismus und Französischer Revolution*, Böhlau, Köln, Weimar, Wien, 2018, p. 339-355.

« L'histoire naturelle dans les marges: écrire dans et à partir des livres. Le cas de Jean Hermann », in Martial GUEDRON and Isabelle LABOULAIS (dir.), *Écrire les sciences. Études sur le XVIII^e siècle*, Bruxelles, Éditions de l'Université de Bruxelles, 2015, p. 81-96.

URL: <https://library.oapen.org/handle/20.500.12657/22264>

Co-edition of a special issue in a peer reviewed journal

« L'herbier selon Rousseau ». Special issue co-edited with Pierre-Emmanuel DuPasquier and Timothée Léchet, *Arts et savoirs* [accepted, 2024].

Publications in preparation

« Le dialogue des objets. Fabrique et circulation des savoirs naturalistes: le cas des collections de Jean Hermann (1738-1800) », PhD thesis, Strasbourg, Maison d'édition scientifique de l'Université de Strasbourg, Collection « Histoire et philosophie des savoirs ».

“Make Nature Visible. The Graphic Representation of the Animal World in Jean Hermann's *Tabula affinitatum animalium* (1783)”.

“The rise of the Globalized Market of Natural History in the Eighteenth-Century Europe: the Forster's family business”.

Research valorisation

Media

« Le dernier herbier de l'écrivain Jean-Jacques Rousseau livre ses secrets aux chercheurs », RTS (Swiss television programme), 10 janvier 2022.

PhD

« Le dialogue des objets. Fabrique et circulation des savoirs naturalistes : le cas des collections de Jean Hermann (1738-1800) – Position de thèse », *Revue d'Alsace*, 145, 2019, p. 341-350.

Publication of sources

« Les riches collections du naturaliste Jean Hermann. Un catalogue raisonné et un recueil de curiosités au XVIII^e siècle », in Rémy CASIN, Jean-Luc EICHENLAUB and Bernadette LITSCHGI (dir.), *Trésors des bibliothèques et archives d'Alsace*, Strasbourg, La Nuée bleue, 2017, p. 273.

«Déchiffrer un dispositif de savoir : le catalogue de la bibliothèque Hermann-Hammer», in Frédéric BARBIER (dir.), *Bibliothèques Strasbourg : origines-XXI^e siècle*, Paris, Éditions des Cendres, Strasbourg, BNU, 2015, p. 235-236.

▪ CONFERENCE PRESENTATIONS

International conferences

With Timothée Léchet and Christian Morel, «L'herbier virtuel Jean-Jacques Rousseau», conference “Uses, practices and functions of historical herbaria”, Ascona, Conference center of Monte Verità, 6-8 November 2023.

“The rise of the Globalized Market of Natural History in the Eighteenth-Century Europe”, symposium of the EUTOPIA Science and Innovation Fellowship, University Pompeu Fabra, Barcelona, 25-27 October 2023.

“Jacob Forster’s Family Business and the Naturalist Market in the Eighteenth-Century Europe”, symposium of the EUTOPIA Science and Innovation Fellowship, Cergy Paris University, 19-21 October 2022.

With Timothée Léchet, « Entre musées et bibliothèques: la patrimonialisation des herbiers de Jean-Jacques Rousseau », 6th Swiss Congress of Historical Sciences, Geneva, 29 June-1st July 2022.

“Make Nature Visible. The Graphic Representation of the Animal World in Jean Hermann’s *Tabula affinitatum animalium* (1783)”, symposium of the European Society for the History of Science, University of Bologna, 31 August-3rd September 2020.

“The Dialogue between Objects in Jean Hermann’s Cabinet (18th century)”, British Society of History of Science, European University Institute, Florence 5-7 April 2017.

“Natural History Collections and Observation in the 18th century: the case of Jean Hermann’s Cabinet”, conference “Collecting and the Knowledge of Objects”, Georg-August University, Göttingen, 5-9 September 2016.

« Observer à partir des collections d’histoire naturelle au XVIII^e siècle. La mise en visibilité des objets au sein du cabinet de Jean Hermann », conference “Devices for a new visual epistemology in the natural sciences (1740-1840)”, University of Neuchâtel, 4-7 November 2015.

« La mise en spectacle du savoir naturaliste : enseigner à partir des collections au XVIII^e siècle. Le cas du professeur Jean Hermann », conference « Die Universität Straßburg zwischen Späthumanismus und Französischer Revolution », Arbeitsstelle für Kulturwissenschaftliche Forschungen, Engi, 4-7 June 2015.

« Commerce matériel et circulation des objets de savoir au XVIII^e siècle: croiser des réseaux européens aux logiques sociales différenciées. Le cas du naturaliste Jean Hermann », 140th Congress of Historical and Scientific Societies, “Networks and Society”, Reims, 27 April-2 May 2015.

« Construire et organiser le savoir naturaliste au XVIII^e siècle: la collection de livres de Jean Hermann », conference « Strasbourg, the book and libraries (15th-21th) », University of Strasbourg, 13-15 October 2014.

« Le commerce matériel du savoir et les réseaux du naturaliste Jean Hermann (1738-1800) », conference “Networks and History”, University of Toulouse, 9-11 April 2014.

« La fabrique et le commerce du savoir: les réseaux et les pratiques du naturaliste Jean Hermann au XVIII^e siècle », conference “Networks and History”, University of Nice-Sophia Antipolis, 26-28 May 2013.

Seminars

“A World of Natural Specimens. The rise of the Globalized Market of Natural History in the Eighteenth-Century Europe”, guest Lecture, CY Advanced Studies, CY Cergy Paris University, 6 June 2023.

« Collectionner les objets de la nature. Réflexions sur la matérialité des pratiques naturalistes au XVIII^e siècle », seminar “The Museum as an object for History”, Paris National Museum of Natural History, 16 March 2023.

URL: <https://objethistoire.hypotheses.org/2199>

« Voir pour savoir: les collections naturalistes au XVIII^e siècle », seminar “History of Knowledge in the modern period », University Paris Cité, 25 November 2022.

« Le spectacle de la nature: les collections de Jean Hermann au XVIII^e siècle », MISHA, University of Strasbourg, 8 September 2022. Exhibition opening lecture: “The collections of Jean Hermann, an exceptional heritage of Strasbourg”, 8 September-16 October 2022.

Discussion of Sophie Rose Tunney’s communication “*Lost and Forgotten between Paris and Brest: Antoine Laurent and the Material History of Plants*”, seminar ESP.ACE, University of Strasbourg, 28 June 2022.

« Travailler avec les objets: le cabinet du naturaliste Jean Hermann au XVIII^e siècle », seminar « The scientific work (1750-1830). Places, gestures and tools », University of Strasbourg, 25 March 2022.

With Thibaud Martinetti, « Fusée-Aublet et l’expédition de Kourou (1762-1764): de l’inventaire à la colonisation des savoirs et des ressources botaniques de Guyane », seminar “Animals and Plants from elsewhere (16th-21th)”, University of Avignon, 7 June 2021.

“The botanical collections of Jean-Jacques Rousseau (1712-1778) at the crossroads between humanities and science”, seminar “Plants and Insects in the Early Modern Period”, University of Hamburg, 27 April 2021.

With Jérémy Tritz, « La numérisation « en l’état » de l’herbier neuchâtelois de Jean-Jacques Rousseau », seminar “Botanical Legacies from the Enlightenment”, University of Neuchâtel, 5 March 2021.

With Pierre-Emmanuel DuPasquier et Timothée Léchet, « L’herbier Rousseau de Neuchâtel forme-t-il une collection scientifique ? Réflexion interdisciplinaire sur l’analyse, la conservation et l’exposition d’un herbier historique », seminar of l’École du Louvre, 14 December 2020.

With Jérémy Tritz, « Traiter un herbier dans le cadre d’un projet pluridisciplinaire : l’herbier Rousseau comme objet botanique et historique », seminar “Botanical Legacies from the Enlightenment”, University of Neuchâtel, 28 September 2020.

« Les voyageurs européens au regard des registres du naturaliste Jean Hermann. Le cabinet comme lieu de sociabilité et ressource de l'économie du savoir au XVIII^e siècle », seminar “Travel and scholarly practices (17th-19th)”, University of Nancy, 25 September 2020.

« Du cabinet au musée : les collections d'histoire naturelle de Jean Hermann au XVIII^e siècle », University of Strasbourg, 2 March 2020.

« L'écriture comme outil de visualisation de la nature. Le dialogue entre les textes et les objets au sein du cabinet de Jean Hermann au XVIII^e siècle », seminar ScriptHis, University of Strasbourg, 11 April 2019.

« L'économie d'échange et la circulation des objets naturalistes dans la correspondance de Jean Hermann au XVIII^e siècle », seminar CORES, University of Besançon, 18-20 June 2018.

« Le professeur strasbourgeois Jean Hermann et ses contacts russes au XVIII^e siècle », seminar “The St-Petersburg Academy of Sciences in the Russia of the Enlightenment”, University of Strasbourg, BNU, 17 October 2017.

« Les collections de Jean Hermann (1738-1800) face au moment révolutionnaire : de la protection à la patrimonialisation », seminar “The French Revolution : a cross-section of historians, teachers and archivists”, Archives départementales du Bas-Rhin, Strasbourg, 26 April 2017.

« Des technologies de papier à la publication d'un discours savant. Le cas du naturaliste Jean Hermann au XVIII^e siècle », seminar “Science, technology, power and society (15th-18th)”, University of Strasbourg, 10 January 2017.

« Les collections comme supports et objets d'inscriptions : les pratiques de l'écrit du naturaliste Jean Hermann au XVIII^e siècle », seminar “Scholars at work. Jean-François Séguier and his correspondants (1703-1784)”, University of Aix-en-Provence, 18-19 November 2016.

With Isabelle Laboulais, « Faire des collections un objet d'histoire sociale des sciences », University of Strasbourg, 3 November 2016.

« Le rôle des images au sein des collections du naturaliste Jean Hermann au XVIII^e siècle », seminar on the History of the Eighteenth-Century Europe, University of Strasbourg, 18 March 2016.

« Construire le savoir minéralogique à partir d'une collection. Le cabinet d'histoire naturelle de Jean Hermann au XVIII^e siècle », University of Strasbourg, 9-12 March 2016.

Workshops

With Timothée Léchet, « Une collection à géométrie variable: l'herbier virtuel Jean-Jacques Rousseau », workshop “Digital processing of botanical collections. For a dialogue between history, computer science and botany”, University of Neuchâtel, 8 October 2021.

“Revealing University Objects: from the Attics to the Public”, Universeum – European Academic Heritage network, Jardin des Sciences, University of Strasbourg, 23-27 May 2016.

« Échanges, circulation et réseaux des objets de savoir. Le cas du naturaliste Jean Hermann (1738-1800) », workshop “Circulation and exchanges in Europe (XIth-XVIIIth)”, University of Tours, 21 May 2014.

«Jean Hermann et les collections d'histoire naturelle à Strasbourg au XVIII^e siècle», University of Strasbourg, 12 October 2012.

Research valorisation

«Sur les traces du naturaliste strasbourgeois Jean Hermann. Comment observer la nature à partir d'un cabinet d'histoire naturelle au XVIII^e siècle?», Zoological Museum of Strasbourg, 2 February 2019.

«Du projet encyclopédique au lieu de savoir. Les collections du naturaliste Jean Hermann (1738-1800)», Colmar Museum of Natural History and Ethnography, 13 October 2017.

«Introduction à l'histoire des sciences. Du métier de chercheur aux perspectives de recherche», seminar of professional development, Maison pour la Science, University of Strasbourg, 9 March 2017.

«Les collections d'histoire naturelle du savant Jean Hermann (1738-1800)», Zoological Museum of Strasbourg, 26 November 2015.

▪ ORGANISATION OF CONFERENCES

International conference “Uses, practices and functions of historical herbaria”, co-organized with Pierre-Emmanuel DuPasquier and Timothée Léchet, Conference center of Monte Verità, Ascona, 6-8 November 2023.

Workshop “Digital processing of botanical collections. For a dialogue between history, computer science and botany”, co-organized with Perrine Baechli and Edouard Di Maio, University of Neuchâtel, 8 October 2021.

▪ EXHIBITIONS

Contribution to the exhibition “The collections of Jean Hermann, an exceptional heritage of Strasbourg”, MISHA, University of Strasbourg, 8 September-16 October 2022.

Exhibition organized with the collaboration of Sylvain Perrot (UMR 7044, MISHA), the Jardin des Sciences, the National University Library of Strasbourg (BNU), the Zoological and Mineralogical museums of Strasbourg. URL: <https://www.misha.fr/agenda/evenement/les-collections-du-naturaliste-jean-hermann-un-patrimoine-strasbourgeois-exceptionnel>

Scientific curator of the exhibition “The collections of Jean Hermann: a natural and cultural heritage”, University of Strasbourg, September 2014.

Exhibition organized with the collaboration of the Jardin des Sciences, the Zoological Museum, the Mineralogical Museum, the Herbarium of the Strasbourg University, the National University Library (BNU) of Strasbourg.

▪ DIGITAL HUMANITIES

Contribution to the design and production of the Jean-Jacques Rousseau virtual herbarium, Sinergia project “Botanical Legacies from the Enlightenment”, University of Neuchâtel, 2020-2023.

Jean-Jacques Rousseau virtual herbarium: <https://lesherbiersderousseau.org>

Contribution to the online platform Oscahr (Science and Society), Jardin des Sciences, University of Strasbourg, 2017-2018. URL : <https://oscahr.unistra.fr>

▪ AWARDS AND FELLOWSHIPS

Post-doctoral fellowship, Marie Curie Skłodowska – EUTOPIA-SIF Co-fund CY Cergy Paris University (France), CY Advanced Studies, Heritage	2022-2024
Post-doctoral fellowship, Swiss National Science Foundation, Sinergia project University of Neuchâtel (Switzerland), Department of Literature and Knowledge	2020-2022
Early Career Fellowship, University of Göttingen (Germany), Lichtenberg-Kolleg (declined) Göttingen Institute for Advanced Study in the Humanities and Social Sciences	
Martin Bucer thesis prize (humanities), St Thomas foundation of Strasbourg	2019
Doctoral fellowship, University of Strasbourg (France) EA 3400 ARCHE, ED 519	2012-2015

▪ RESEARCH VISITS

Visiting research fellow, University of Warwick Department of History, Global History and Culture Centre	April-May 2024`
Visiting research fellow, Conservatory and Botanical Garden of Geneva (Switzerland) Digitization of the Jean-Jacques Rousseau's herbarium held at the Public Library of Neuchâtel (3 weeks)	2021-2022
Visiting research fellow, Paris National Museum of Natural History (France) Inventory and study of the Rousseau-Fusée-Aublet's herbarium	2020

▪ SOCIETIES

Member of the European Society for the History of Science	2020-today
Member of the Swiss Society of History	2022-today

TEACHING EXPERIENCE

▪ CY CERGY PARIS UNIVERSITY 2022-2024

Bachelor's degree – History:

States, powers and disputes (1643-1793)
Tutored projects

▪ UNIVERSITY OF STRASBOURG 2014-2019

Bachelor's degree – History, Archaeology, Art History and Humanities:

History of modern Europe (16th-18th)

University methodology
Professional project
Cultural History of modern Europe (16th-18th)
History of collections and museums (16th-19th)
Book history
History of Natural History (16th-19th)

Master's degree – History, History of Science, MEEF:

Epistemology and History of Science
Heritage and objects
Professional teaching units

SKILLS

▪ **LANGUAGES**

French: native language

English: fluent

German: scholar level

▪ **COMPUTER SKILLS**

Office software: Ms Office suites

Database software: Access, Filemaker

Network analysis and visualisation software: NodeXL, Pajek

Digital edition software (historical documents): Oxygen XML editor

Cartomatic and vector graphics software: Philcarto, Adobe Illustrator